

HISTORICAL REALITY IN THE OLD WORLD NOVEL AND MENTAL IMAGE SYNTHESIS

Isayeva Shoirra

Associate professor, candidate of philological sciences
Alisher Navo'i Tashkent State University of Uzbek language and
literature (TSUULL)

shoiraisayeva1960@gmail.com

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ANNOTATION

The 20th century the last quarter is Uzbek novel real reality whole complexity with cover get and him own fresh , own direction and in conflicts reflection to continue with character changed . Most the important thing is that epic reality image with characters the spirit image synthesized . Epic in the narration psyche of the image increase , different so to speak , of reality characters the psyche historical image through reflection delivered present Uzbek in his novel of psychology from development proof will give .

Key words: *dramatic image, characters activity, legality action, cultural environment;*

This is the process epic , lyrical and dramatic image methods natural , unique in harmony coming characters the psyche more deeper , more more reasonable and more reliable open of giving method and tools wealth because of done increased Uzbek novel in nature such quality o' changes while of the genre more and more vital to polyphony approaching that it is going means Uzbek in his novel characters the psyche deep and comprehensive in lighting Odil Yakubov's share weighty He is Abdullah Qadiri , Oybek , Abdulhamid Cholpons starting from gave classic realistic from our novel psychological image the principle is both modern and historical in topics from novels one how much higher raised .

L. Ginzburg about respectively emphasized psychological novel or in the novel my psychologist randomness necessity the most higher level requires adaptation .

Odil Yakubov « Old This is what the novel " world " is all about harmony to provide achieved , any randomness and necessity psyche in the image today's the reader convince took.

According to the first method in the work this to the character the author speech , again being described situation and from the situation come out in case the author image through to the character description to give strives However this Method O. Yakubov 's novels for that much typical it's not . To this end u,, Old in the work " world " less occurs .

Second method according to characters activity and novel characters to the psyche look with approaching them criteria through evaluates . O. Yakubov in his novels in the work to the characters another characters by price give , more precisely by doing in other words , he or this character to the psyche different characters the spirit through look to throw perfect processed artistic method such as not shown . This is the method while each in the work character the psyche believable , important while student for interesting one way objective to evaluate possibility will give .

" Ko'hna ." in the novel " World ". characters the spirit image to the analysis enter before again one to the matter briefly stopping transition need will be Scientific in the literature psyche image colorful about it concepts before is pushed . For example, Russian psychological of the school large appearance D. N. Ovsyanikov - Kulikovskiy of creators characters in the

image spirit , strength expenses stop them two to the group separated was These are : objective and subjective from creators consists of His in his opinion , objective creators themselves created the most good characters the psyche in opening directly their to themselves typical was , is being described events from logic come out , in cases in them psyche their own spiritual features sure objective though to describe they strive Of this bright example It is I. S. Turgenev . Objective creators characters the spirit in the image from themselves spiritual strength they don't spend .

Writers of the second type D. N. Ovsyanikov Kulikovsky subjective creators said . Such creators themselves created characters the psyche in opening directly to themselves typical or near spiritual in terms of feelings come out they describe . Subjective creators psyche in the image very a lot spiritual power they spend Of this bright example as L. N. Tolstoy brings Of course it is scientific approach based on certain observations , many literary images generalization is lying down However, we O. Yakubov in his work , in particular historical in his novels characters the psyche in lighting to himself characteristic from this above said from conception come came out without price we give Because , first of all , any artistic creativity own to the point according to subjective is a process . Therefore , the creator is either this character the psyche in opening one in place work events from logic come came out without objective chronological determinism requirements compliance did without the work kòrsa , other one in place characters to logic suitable personal experiences through subjective price to give strives By this we mean that the creator own role skillfully play if possible to the actor like one in place psyche in the image objective evaluation by way of if it goes , the second one in place subjective to evaluate appeal will be done . From this come coming out conclusion that is , a writer in his work characters the spirit subjective relationship joining and playing together goes Otherwise let's say , O. Yakubov's " Old in the novel " world " . characters the spirit secret to an ambivalent character have This is the ambivalent feature while characters the psyche sure to lighting possibility will give . To this end psyche ambivalence (contradiction) organize is enough.

Secondly , he is a realist artist for feelings realism ideas , thoughts from realism is important . Of this because that is , the characters the psyche today complexity (ambivalence) , the whole edges with open to give creative for certain gòyani or the idea to say basis will give . That 's it to legality action did adib « Kokhna Mahmud Ghaznavi , Beruni , Ibn Sina , Ibn Shahwani , Malikul Own the wine too feeling experiences , behavior through to open strives This is the process while from literature sometimes too objective attitude , sometimes very subjective requires attitude .

As you know , write a historical novel to himself typical complicated there are sides . Especially Abu Rayhan Like Beruni , Ibn Sina to the world known and famous scientists life , work lighting from the creator big responsibility , they lived historical and political environment and common way anyway , that's it scientists created scientific works about right requires imagination . " Old In the novel " world " O. Yakubov is like that heavy and complicated to work hand hits and his able to came out Roman's in creation this writer in front standing the most heavy from tasks is one.

X century the end and Khorasan until the 30s of the 11th century rule did strongman Sultan Mahmud Ghaznavi during living creativity did Medium Asian two huge scientist life and their activities from the beginning forgave heavy difficult their lives , that's it life under the influence of they are both light and heavy spiritual to the inventors full experiences historical

and artistic to the truths the opposite not coming way believable from describing consists of was On the one hand , during another countries and to the nations danger put standing terrible , in it economic and political and cultural environment , that's it in the environment day forgiving Beruni, Mustabid from the sultan running away , suffering day pardoned by Ibn Sina, as well as Mahmud Ghaznavi characters spiritual complexity with in describing writer leader historical concept catch standing without free artistic plot Create out of the way goes For this reason from the novel sure biographical fact and requesting information it won't happen . Free artistic do n't cut it based on plot from the line while pure historical detailed reality too, pure historical and biographical fact with artistic and spiritual the fact one thing by doing it won't happen ;

Second side, two great allama life and of activity within a novel artistic generalization and full reflection carry on possible it's not. That's why also for Mahmud Ghaznavi in the novel of life the last one year events support chrontop as described Sultan's one umr Ibn Sinani chase stubborn , stubborn and proud of a scientist his from the pursuit run away and hide walking such as historical fact in the work of the sultan heavy to illness it is played from pain only Ibn Sino get rid of do it get it , that's it because of him catch to come aspiration history that given , this thing is Mahmud Ghaznavi and Ibn Sina of conflict vitality , trustworthiness , etc at the time to drama height provides .

Third on the other hand , in the novel all characters from each other sharp different standing persons as is described . Because , Sultan with Beruni between Collisionally , sultan between Ibn Sina publicly conflict novel events dynamics for full enough was But that's it of conflict the solution provide , this of the solution vitality justification in order to aspra Malikul Wine . Piri Bukri , Abu Shilkim ibn Shahvani , Ali Stranger of conflict his cheerfulness one how many characters between conflicts with depends in case centrality due to the composition of the novel a little scattered it seems But work repeatedly if it is read , it is in it between characters different paints , various spiritual image methods through expressed realize get difficult it's not . Characters the psyche mutual certain in conflicts comparison , i.e images parallelism using they are between struggles describe out of the way went writer Beruni and Mahmoud Ghaznavi between tangled relationships sure believable to open wide place will give . Of course it is in the image Beruni character leader place holds and work many events characters look through is evaluated . Beruni while scientist , he is every event or person his own thought experience through , spiritual analysis through evaluates . To this end of the novel the first from the beginning writer his own psyche in the image favorite method level raised remember method appeal is enough The same that's it method asa Beruni character typical leader is a feature . Because he is a scientist as not only scientific problems , maybe his own past , each clicked step and himself known , known , in communication was individuals own from the analysis spends . The same one at the time spiritual of the process wide spread out this method novel characters one after another plot events come in let them come opens . First of the chapter in itself remember method through the events of the novel development significant influence showing Pirn Bukri , Baba Khurmo , Abolqasim Ferdavsi , Nargiza bonu , Malikul wine such as persons life , admiral a believer to the title deserves was Sultan Mahmud Ghaznavi about artistic information is given

Malikul Wine in his youth of the sultan from relatives being , ten four live Nargizabanu reason from the palace distance , his father amir Take it easy loyal nadimi Kuglu from the step the rest pub with livelihood to do , this to the pub Firdausi , Unsuri , Piri Rijjakiy , Piri Bukri

such as scientist of poets , musicians and singers visit order , there until tongotaar passing conversation - parties all of them remind will be passed .

Including Firdausi 's Shahnama the sultan by good unappreciated , his comic writing to the sultan by himself from the treasury out leaving that's it in front of you to the pub entered , Malikul to wine karate said pain full words are stubborn nature and proud actions directly remember by means of given : " Malikul" . wine ! - they said teacher then , in the race stop , - poor man you with poem sultan My brother Ferdowsi not in his pocket never praise psalm reading I will drink , if you don't give me on my lips laugh , inside me pray so , the tavern leave etamen !... Ibn Malikul wine ! Poor sarcastically no , dear I cry !... That's why this humrah the sultan Ghaznavi gave all gifts gados and to the poor I shared ! One day without leaving Did you share it , here it is , my angel som , like a baby dirty-naked , own to my country I rode !.. ». Ferdowsi from the language said above words remember thirty year during effort smoking , huge epic created a poet and of a scientist value that he did not find it , his value good knew this genius rebellion means as the world leave arrival of the sultan poetry , science appreciate can't such as characteristics lighting for service did That 's it after Malikul wine in memory of the sultan second one the victim is Bobo Khurmo comes to life Once upon a time just big to the palm grove have has been nor Mahmoud Ghaznavi by unjustly pulling taken , his instead Garden Feruz set up done because of trade to the case down the rest this a person own in the language honestly justice installer horn about dress up speaking walks How many interesting historical of individuals adventures just story by doing to give with their real their faces to the person mysterious which shows , in his memory patterned stay one image Create possible it's not . Historical of individuals complete characters in creating , eng First of all , theirs spiritual the world , the heart experiences artistic analysis and interpretation reach necessary Without it historical character colorless one to the line turning around remains . To this end especially our artists To O. Yakubov like mature of my writers historical in his novels characters the psyche to open the reader being described historical reality into deeper take access more important .

In the novel events to the stream « giant black to the spider like ” Piri Bukri's come in coming with memory focus From Khorezm a slave by doing take bride To Sadafbibi will move . Own of the country especially Beruni this the girl to himself current received , but Piri Bukri's this sad the girl chase to do in the novel between characters of conflicts intense to be described possibility gave

Young a dancer Nargizabanu because of with Amir Mahmud Malikul wine in the middle being passed terrible event and Take it easy from the presence of Expulsion , Mahmoud Ghaznavi with Malikul wine in the middle friendship relationship I'm done find it intense to describe possibility will give .

In the work leader of conflict determiner at the node Sultan Mahmud Ghaznavi stands He is Khorezm conquest after that , to Ma'mun offer from there large scientists , art people captive so , own the capital To the treasury take will come . However, he is famous later , " admiral " mominin " title After receiving , Unsuri such as the palace to his servants goodwill showing scientists from the situation message without taking put Your life At the end of heavy to pain plague was the sultan own cure only for Ibn Sinani Let's look for it , Beruni and another scientists to the palace collects

Fame and to students full the navqiran boyhood years Remembering is hard illness because of nights awake transfer What memories do you have ? to the vortex does not shoot .

Sultan so to the blue down the rest There so of nights in one he went to the consulting room come in remains and today room across defeated was of branches gold silver , crown and weapons out of sight sorry it's a girl of the kingdom regions expand for take went fight accelerated , bowed to him military commanders remembers His in memory of the King of Kashmir with was battle will come . Sultan himself defeated reached branches remembering how much proud , huge this state the owner when one gratuitous pain that 's it to the blue put hard pain does

Writer of the sultan this memory of the work wanted from where not but commemoration for very comfortable one in the situation brings Because a person the spirit so one controversial to the feature yes , he is happy in them the most unhappy the rest is unhappy in them while the most happy the holidays remembers Man to the psyche that 's how it is controversial of the situation believable output while of the work another one instead not but the same that's it awake yesterday , from the branches memory being the rest gold and silver items , weapons watch to do during face to give more natural came out In the novel Abu Basil Beruni memories determiner lines important have He is himself in the hut with a fever lie down it 's childhood past Jayhun beaches , one hug firewood under basis knocking coming tibia mother remembers He is his mother Abu Save Christian from the skirt holding science take the necessity , then mother from passing rescue possible about their training remembers

Scientist in memory sealed the rest events in the novel three fulfills the task . The first of Beruni simple hard worker from the family growing up coming out , in childhood very a lot labor is hard work smoking and that's it hardships because of mature allama being that it is known accuracy if entered , the second to a person typical feature while traveling , patient without - remaining person's in memory of youth and Masud holidays from coming consists of spiritual the experience from giving consists of This kind of memoryless , mental stateless of a scientist in the heart alone , patient without fever in Ogushi alahsirab to lie down impressive describing to give possible it's not . Aks without , image live , objective not but dry note from doing consists of being remains was

of Beruni in memory suddenly teacher Christian from the lessons enjoy Rayhon 's father merchant in his house spent the days of the merchant death reach , Piri Bukri's To Raykhan the abandonment of Beruni poor thing the girl saved stay , recite Khorezmshokh by pressing to be taken , a lot without passing Urganj leave reached Jurjon , Ray and in Hamadan workman wandering around when walking Basil's from the world pass such as from each other heavy memories it both tortures him and calms him give was To each other opposite such experience and memories Beruni soul of processes ambivalence to describe service the third is the spirit of the image remember method of characters different edges to open possibility gave Memories person own to the vortex one did he pull , from him get rid of difficult Especially the patient person alone in the cell with a fever when lying down memories to memories connecting keeps going Theirs one happy doer , other one while sad and painful will be Thus Abu Basil Beruni memories of the heart enlightened doer in memory - about Ibn Sina to events connecting goes He is Abu With Ali Sino from this ten five a year ago passed the meeting remembers At that time Ibn Sina Beruni was Mahmud Ghaznavi to the presence of from going back , own their fates together try to see invitation reached was However Beruni a little rest in peace , Sultan shelter science to do looking forward to it to the proposal not added was The end consequence what being came out : himself thinking walked scientific of work quite a few done increased , but strongman the sultan in the palace anyway himself very to

science mobile to do reach didn't get it . Ibn Shahvani in the palace, Abol Hasan Unsuri such as conspirator officials and flatterers at every step , every moment his plans halal they give was And this science man for very painful , humiliating with equal to was About Ibn Sina bright memories with him get along suspicion because of dim pulled Writer This is Beruni in moments situation the psyche very appropriate experiences with concludes : " Beruni in the brain dim candle off , it's clearer candles to turn on long Tried , no candle lit , it's over in the end dimmed remains , in his heart bright memories painful , restless thoughts with exchanged » (p. 115).

So , the character spirit , mood social reality personal life with depends in case different kind of memories to remember leads But this memories of the person himself such as mysterious , hopeless spirit with is exchanged . That 's it natural the situation writer Beruni character to himself characteristic of each thing , each step ok thinking pressing scientist nature whole complexity with to lighting mobile does

Historical character essence attention with certain historical period , historical reality product That's it period , reality in the shell sure and believable describe historical to the work typical feature is considered For a historical novel character historicity period , reality with conditioned without his spiritual the world various districts cases describe important To this end O. Ekubov << Kitchen every one in the world historical color the character spiritual in cases , conditions to describe strives That 's it in terms of remembering Ibn Sina's character from the method some edges filling fruitful is used . Amir Masud's assignment with Ibn Sina special Kurik players under control to the treasury will be sent . They are Hamadan nearby one in the field the tent sewing they are satisfied . Ibn Sina from the tent at night out and around becomes Marrow at night spins it's the same so marrow at night Bukhara steppes , Afshona around them right Added in a cart mother Sitorabonu with road press and they are in the middle being passed conversation his remember falls Because space and in time similarity associative way of a scientist childhood with oi in years being won one the night remember puts That's when Sitorabonu of mind to the mind let's go it 's good to stay prayers did . After conversations uncle's big daughter To Gulrukhsar go was wearing Young Abu Ali in the morning favorite Gulrukhsar his sister to see in his passion burning and panting sleeping the rest was But in the morning his sister alive to see fate it was not enough . There then mother good judges about he spoke Abu Ali's being a good judge to grow that's when the dream comes true born was

Apparently apparently , a writer of the work that's it in the episode remember method space and in time to similarity based on used Hamadan nearby this of the steppe cashews , grasses shape , smell , night warm and Ibn Sina 's indifference Bukhara steppes villages and dear Legend reminds It is associative condition his to the mind of his mother conversation , good saw sister Gulrukhsar's scientist in his clutches helpless that he left , that's it ominous first thing in the morning heard the word "judge". magic and opportunity about determined feels deeply , imagination his whole fate set will give .

As a great judge medicine drugs about thoughts his remember another memories puts Student Ubayd al- Jurjani with drugs about interview , " Joyi Mulion " street " Dorush " at the end healing » and teacher Abu Mansur Qamari with in the freezer from the world eye closed one get married corpse crack what they saw his from memory will pass

Remember method with above said memories revive by Ibn Sina known to the world doctor being to grow ease with done not increased , this there is a lot of it on the road

hardships that he smoked to the reader known do , i.e to the character of Ibn Sina at the time typical all edges to lighting writer strives Because his in memory events in his memory three points are separate emphasizing will be passed . The first good saw Gulrukhsar of his sister lack of a good judge because of early die leaving That's it to be a good judge covenant did was , until others are good too saw from her sisters separated do n't stay In youth to the covenant loyal to stay and to pay it to the character of Ibn Sina typical determination , loyalty proof will give .

The second is any medicinal drug drugs without knowing be a good judge ca n't That's why it's a field wandering around eats , theirs content learns and of them drug prepares So , Ibn Sina himself superlative relentlessly working specialist The third a person members , each the disease treatment methods one gyoh , one while nashtar with treatment to do ways not knowing he deeply feels that he will not be a good judge . That is why he is a teacher From Abu Mansur Qamari corpses light up and scientist reasons determination according to education takes Of judgement higher it is easy to level with reach didn't get : initially from the corpse was afraid , then after finally learned . So remember the memory from revitalization consists of

Writer a person to the psyche typical this the process historical to the characters traits in full lighting them alive people as their faces live to create is watching and to this will achieve . Maybe Ibn Sina's to the world famous doctor and scientist being to grow Entirely different maybe gone But O. Yakubov all real of judges occupation take over the process is similar that it was based on art imagination power with own to the goal achieves Because Ibn Sina's character historicity the fact is that he is mature scientist , peerless judge. In legend birth found in Bukhara studied in Khorezm Ma`mun in the Academy Khorezm Mahmud Ghaznavi worked by pressing after taking , his refusing to serve , Iran Afghanistan on the borders running away walking , his own famous his works wrote Scientist to his life that 's what it is things to the chroniclers like dry note reach artistic work according to nature . To this end writer historical characters life and to the activity typical main of images artistry character spiritual the world lighting through provided. That therefore writer historical characters life and to the activity typical main from the direction did not retreat without his artistic appearance in full tries to know. First , Ibn Sina, Beruni such as historical persons the psyche to give help giver sure data no . That's why for writer of characters essence , activity and historical from the data using the spirit in the image free but artistic logic requirements based on the work sees Artistic in creation historical characters the psyche describe the most tested the way from that consists of

Like Beruni , Mahmud Ghaznavi , Ibn Sina historical and Malikul wine such as artistic fabric characters spiritual experiences their own to the past about memories remember through in describing writer a person of your mind chain rings such as continuously flow natural to give strives That 's it thing , that is character in the psyche passing events in the stream one munqli , one Good luck , again one while too rebellious events each other with makes sense in connection to give achieves " Old world » of the novel poetics special research ethane E. Rahimov in the novel memories remember in the process mind flow to give of the writer aspiration and to this achieved to the issue stopping the following when he wrote full right was : " In literary studies good price received Murad Muhammad Do`st , Oman Autonomous to novels typical feature occupation reached mind flow process in fact Fair Yakubov's " Old in the work " world ". of experiences makes sense is continued ". Indeed ,

either of the characters this the event memories in the process statement their look neither speech through take will go Actually and that 's it statement writer and character statement together goes However the author statement character statement behind hiding that there is book reader feeling stands Unexpectedly this statement the author statement with , the author and character statement while memory inside characters statement with together goes This is how it is in the novel statement a lot sonority occupation is enough Polyphonic in the image memories continuously without to be given a person nature typical mind of flow writer by successful give get skill from the height proof will give .

From this except , continuous mind flow in the style of being described in memory of events to each other opposite character occupation reach writer by applied spiritual of the image meditation , philosophical thought , internal speech and analysis , recall such as types spiritual analysis principle in the novel leader position from possession proof will give . In the novel psyche of the image to himself feature his one of time both visual and analytical mutual synthesized in case is given.

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